

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		22/11/2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		Hou et al.	
Country of origin		China	
Publication year		2019	
Title of article		The Effectiveness and Safety of Utilizing Mobile Phone-Based Programs for Rehabilitation After Lumbar Spinal Surgery: Multicenter, Prospective Randomized Controlled Trial	
Title of journal		JMIR Mhealth Uhealth	
Volume 7	Issue 2	Pages 1-14	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Title, abstract, p.2
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	Agreed to receive lumbar spinal surgery and that the surgical intervention involved no more than 3 columns Diagnosed as lumbar disc herniation, spinal stenosis, or lumbar spondylolisthesis with imaging support	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 3, textbox 1
Types of intervention	Mobile Phone based electronic health program	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 3
Types of comparison	Usual care treatment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2

Types of outcome measures	Function disability/status, back pain, mental health and life status,	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	To investigate whether a mobile phone-based program (electronic health; eHealth), designed to provide telerehabilitation for patients with LBP, would reduce pain-related disability and improve prognosis among postoperative patients who have no access to traditional clinic-based rehabilitation.	p. 2
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	Multicenter, prospective, randomized controlled trial	p. 2
Start date	August 2013	p. 4
End date	November 2014	p. 4
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes No Unclear Approved by the Ethics Committees of the Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital.	p. 2

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	All the 3 hospitals that participated in this study were affiliated to the Sun Yat-sen University, where the surgery could be carried out safely and skilfully.	p. 2
Inclusion criteria	Aged between 18 and 64 years, agreed to receive lumbar spinal surgery and that the surgical intervention involved no more than 3 columns, diagnosed as lumbar disc herniation, spinal stenosis, or lumbar spondylolisthesis with imaging support, living at least 100 km or a 2 hours' drive away from the hospitals, and signed the informed consent	p. 3, textbox 1
Exclusion criteria	Diagnosed as tuberculosis and tumor patients, those who accepted lumbar surgeries before this trial, patients with rheumatoid arthritis or ankylosing spondylitis, pregnancy, and those who could not sign the informed consent or complete the rehabilitation exercise because of mental retardation or other reasons	p. 3, textbox 1

Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes No Unclear		p. 3, textbox 1
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Intervention group

Copy and paste table for each intervention and comparison group

Intervention Group 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Intervention group - eHealth	p. 3
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	84 – 24 patients lost to follow up → 60 patients Mean age = 51.11	p. 5, Figure 2 p. 6 Table 1

<p>Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)</p>	<p>Besides the relevant surgeons' usual practice, patients randomized to the intervention group received telerehabilitation provided by eHealth, a mobile phone-based system developed by our group. Moreover, eHealth was designed based on the user-centered theory, aimed to provide a platform for the delivery of self-management interventions. It contained 2 interfaces: a mobile phone-based interface for patients and a Web-based interface for doctors. Through the mobile phone-based interface, patients were able to view the rehabilitation plans made by their physicians and conduct their rehabilitation following the video instructions. In addition, patients could receive daily reports about their exercise and alerts to prompt them to return to this system. They could also communicate with their doctors through this system. Through the Web-based interface, the doctors could adjust rehabilitation plans for patients and view reports about the patients' daily exercise. All data were synchronized and stored in a remote server. The exercises included in this software were designed based on core stability exercise principles, which were all aimed to restore normal muscle strength and mobility, to activate the deep core musculature and to promote balance and coordination of the patients' daily movements. The validation study was conducted with 10 healthy adults. Then, the information for the usability of the system was collected through paper-based questionnaires, 1 day after the tryout. The validation study confirmed that our system was well designed and easy to use, and the rehabilitation guidance was easy for users to understand. Combined with the results of previous studies and user preferences, our study set the rehabilitation for 20 min each time, twice a day.</p> <p>The software was installed into the patients' phones 3 months after the surgery. Two meetings were held to show the patients how to use this software and how to conduct the exercises. The patients were also evaluated to make sure they can conduct the rehabilitation exercise correctly. They were required to complete at least 2 months of training. After 2 months, the patients could still log on to the system, and those who completed 5 or more training sessions each week were considered as high adherence, 3 to 5 training sessions as medium adherence, and 2 training sessions and less as low adherence.</p>	<p>p. 3</p>
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Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Usual care group	p. 3
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	84 allocated – 61 at 24 months follow-up Mean age = 49.36	p. 5, Figure 2 p. 6 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	No specific rehabilitation program was provided to patients randomized to the UC control group. The relevant surgeons' usual practice was still provided, including advices to keep physically active and simple instructions to train the back muscles. Analgesia and other symptomatic treatments were also provided when necessary. All the postoperative regimes were documented.	p. 3

Outcomes

Outcome 1 Primary Outcome

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	ODI	Abstract, p. 3
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Function Favors intervention	p. 3

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	VAS	Abstract, p. 3, p. 4. p. 5 table 1, p. 6, p. 7, table 3, p. 9 table 9
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Back pain Favors intervention	p. 3

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Likert score	Abstract, p. 3, p. 6 table 1, p. 7, p. 8 table 4
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Movement	

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	EQ-5D, SF36	Abstract, p. 3, p. 6, p. 7. P. 8 table 4
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Mental health and life status Favors intervention	p. 3

Follow up

Follow up	24 months	Abstract, p. 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, p 8 table 4
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	In conclusion, eHealth, a mobile phone-based telerehabilitation system, may be an effective rehabilitation tool for postoperative patients with LBP, especially for those who have no access to traditional clinic-based rehabilitation. The effectiveness of eHealth was more evident in patients with higher adherence. However, more studies are still needed to find optimal methods to improve compliance.	p. 10

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>